

OPTIMIZATION OF MICRODISTRICT DRAINAGE SYSTEMS: SANITARY AND ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS FOR RESIDENTS

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Abstract. *The article examines the methods and models of optimal placement of drainage systems within residential microdistricts. The task of optimal drainage allocation is closely related to the optimization of housing infrastructure, contributing to the integration of these parameters into optimization problems in the context of urbanization processes.*

The study considers both international and domestic practices, as well as scientific approaches to the organization of drainage system operations.

Keywords: *drainage systems and their types, housing infrastructure, urbanization, optimization, regional economy, microdistrict drainage time.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada mikrorayon hududida drenaj tizimini optimal joylashtirish usullari va modellari tadqiq etilgan. Drenajlarni optimal joylashtirish vazifasi turar-joy infratuzilmasini optimallashtirish masalalari bilan bog'liq bo'lib, bu jarayon urbanizatsiya jarayonlarini hisobga olgan holda optimallashtirish masalalarida parametrlarni inobatga olishga xizmat qiladi.*

Maqolada drenaj tizimlari ishini ilmiy tashkil etish bo'yicha xalqaro va mahalliy tajribalar ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *drenaj tizimi va ularning turlari, turar-joy infratuzilmasi, urbanizatsiya, optimallashtirish, mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot, mikrorayon maydonini quritish vaqti.*

Аннотация. *В статье исследуются методы и модели оптимального размещения дренажной системы на территории жилого микрорайона. Задача оптимального размещения дренажей связана с задачами оптимизации жилищной инфраструктуры, что способствует учету данных параметров в оптимизационных задачах с учетом процессов урбанизации.*

В статье рассматриваются международные и отечественные практики и опыт научной организации работы дренажных систем.

Ключевые слова: *дренажная система и их типы, жилищная инфраструктура, урбанизация, оптимизация, региональная экономика, время осушения территории микрорайона.*

INTRODUCTION

In the context of intensive growth of residential settlements and densification of housing development, the problem of excessive soil moisture is becoming increasingly urgent. Insufficient drainage leads to the destruction of foundations, flooding of basements, accelerated corrosion of engineering networks, and a decline in the quality of life of the population.

The problem of soil salinization and waterlogging has become one of the most widespread and relevant in recent years, including in residential microdistricts. Therefore, it is

necessary to comprehensively study the key problems in this field, identify solutions, including the installation and reconstruction of drainage systems, as well as analyze existing models. Such an approach makes it possible to identify gaps in existing research and outline directions for their elimination in subsequent works.

Historically, drainage systems were considered primarily as a tool for removing excess moisture from the soil. Underground drains have been used for millennia, but their large-scale application began only in the second half of the 20th century, when empirical knowledge in land reclamation and salinity control received a solid theoretical foundation. Over the past forty years, the role of drainage systems has changed significantly: from a narrowly focused means of combating waterlogging and salinization, they have transformed into an important element of the comprehensive task of optimizing housing stock and microdistrict infrastructure.

The city of Tashkent and several regional centers of the republic have recently faced a number of serious hydrogeological challenges. The rise of groundwater levels, caused by both natural and anthropogenic factors, has led to a systemic deterioration in the technical condition of urban facilities.

The main problems recorded during surveys in Yunusabad, Sergeli, and Gulistan districts include:

- rise of groundwater levels (GWL) to 1.5–2.0 m in some areas;
- appearance of cracks in building walls due to foundation subsidence;
- increased morbidity among the population associated with high humidity indoors;
- basement flooding, failure of heating and sewer systems;
- shortage of land suitable for development due to the risk of waterlogging.

Climatic influences are also observed — high summer temperatures, sharp humidity fluctuations, low winter precipitation, and heavy rains in spring and summer require a revision of approaches to engineering infrastructure.

One of the effective tools for engineering protection of microdistrict territories are drainage systems of various types — horizontal, vertical, area-based, and linear. The implementation of drainage ensures the stability of buildings and structures and improves ecological and sanitary safety.

If drainage systems are not applied in the operation of residential microdistricts, the results may be negative:

Consequence of non-application	Probable result
Rise of groundwater level	Foundation flooding, dampness in basements
Waterlogging	Lawn destruction, mosquito growth, mold
Road surface damage	Subsidence, cracks, accidents
Damage to engineering networks	Leaks, short circuits, emergency shutdowns, pipe corrosion
Increase in residents' morbidity	Bronchopulmonary, allergic, and fungal diseases
Growth of building restoration costs	Up to 1.5–2 billion UZS per year per microdistrict

Thus, the main task is:

- classification of drainage systems applicable under dense microdistrict development;

- determination of drainage influence on the technical condition of housing stock and engineering infrastructure of microdistricts;
- development and implementation of algorithms for optimal introduction of various drainage systems, minimizing groundwater impact on housing and sanitary conditions of microdistricts.

Compliance with established standards and requirements is a necessary condition. Considering that optimization of drainage systems is interconnected with optimization of housing and infrastructure of microdistricts, models must be developed to adequately reflect the objectives and tasks of various types of drainage systems.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

In the context of modern urbanization and increasing residential density, ensuring effective water drainage and maintaining sanitary and ecological standards is one of the priority tasks of urban planning practice. In both international and domestic science, a significant body of research has been accumulated on drainage systems in residential neighborhoods, which can conditionally be divided into three directions: engineering and technical solutions, environmentally oriented concepts, and regional applied studies.

A significant contribution to the formation of the scientific foundations of drainage systems has been made by both domestic and foreign researchers, whose works are aimed at creating environmentally safe and sanitary-friendly living conditions in the urban environment. For instance, at the Institute of Hydrogeology and Engineering Geology (Uzbekistan), research is being conducted on the development of new methods for forecasting, assessing, and rationally using groundwater resources, as well as creating an optimal monitoring system based on modern GIS technologies. In the design and research institution “UzGIP,” projects are being implemented for the design of drainage systems in accordance with technical specifications. Special attention should be paid to the works of A. Karimov, dedicated to the problem of flooding in the city of Tashkent.

Among the scientists of the CIS countries, S.K. Abramov (Russia) [1] should be noted, who studied the classification and principles of drainage system functioning, as well as developed methods of hydrogeological calculations used to determine the necessity of their installation. His works address issues of construction and operation of drainage systems in various natural and climatic conditions, as well as the protection of industrial and civil facilities from flooding. An important contribution was also made by B.M. Degtyarev (Russia), who summarized domestic and foreign experience in protecting soil foundations of buildings and structures from the impact of groundwater, which leads to a reduction in their bearing capacity [2].

A.G. Ragimova (Russia) identified patterns of drainage and changes in the soil profile, showing that a universal theoretical solution to drainage problems is impossible, and well-grounded engineering solutions on site remain essential [7].

Foreign research is mainly focused on the search for innovative and environmentally oriented solutions. For example, R. Eggelsmann (Germany) studied the application of volumetric drainage filters that increase inflow and prevent system silting. The works of W. Ratnayake (Ireland) and W. Sirishanta (Sri Lanka) are devoted to the development of stormwater management strategies in cities using modern methods of drainage flow regulation.

Scientists M.N. Torres and J.P. Rodriguez Sanchez (Colombia) are conducting research on the implementation of decision support systems for managing sustainable urban drainage systems.

The studies of Ritzema H.P. (Netherlands) focus on subsurface flows into drains, the principles, and applications of drainage [8].

In Uzbekistan, the problem of drainage systems is considered in the context of sustainable development of Tashkent and other major cities. Domestic research is more oriented toward engineering calculations and the adaptation of drainage systems to local natural and technogenic conditions (climate, groundwater level, building density), whereas foreign developments are focused on integrating drainage solutions with ecological infrastructure and managing the quality of the urban environment.

Thus, modern research on drainage systems demonstrates methodological diversity: from classical engineering algorithms to environmentally oriented concepts. For the conditions of Uzbekistan, the most promising approach appears to be a combined one, integrating engineering methods of groundwater and surface water drainage with elements of “green infrastructure,” which makes it possible to reduce the load on existing drainage networks and improve the sanitary and ecological living conditions of the population.

METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

The methodological foundation of the study is based on the principles of the theory of urbanization, a systemic approach to managing the development of urban areas and housing infrastructure, as well as methods for developing economic-mathematical models of drainage systems as an integral part of residential settlements [3].

The research methodology includes economic-mathematical modeling to determine the optimal parameters of drainage systems, taking into account the tasks of optimizing the housing stock and neighborhood infrastructure; the types and methods of placing drainage systems within residential areas under conditions of urbanization; as well as methods of generalization and classification, comparative and dynamic analysis, systems approach, and statistical analysis.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The main tasks of drainage in a residential neighborhood are to lower the groundwater level and drain the area, improve soil conditions, and ensure normal growth of green spaces.

Drainage, as an element of ecological infrastructure [5]:

- ensures the preservation of living conditions within the neighborhood and mitigates adverse environmental impacts;

- plays an important role in ensuring normal and safe living conditions for the population by protecting infrastructure facilities (medical institutions – hospitals, polyclinics; educational institutions – kindergartens, schools, etc.; trade and consumer services – shops, markets, hairdressers, etc.; housing infrastructure – residential buildings, dormitories, hotels; sports grounds; sewerage and water supply);

- provides comfortable living and favorable conditions for the development of the neighborhood’s social infrastructure by preventing the negative effects of excess moisture on social infrastructure facilities, improving residents’ living conditions, and creating a favorable sanitary environment;

- lowers the groundwater level, regulates filtration in the built-up area, and ensures drainage of the neighborhood territory to prepare it for construction;

– is capable of extending the service life of building foundations up to fifty years or more.

The need to implement a drainage system in a neighborhood requires formalizing this task, developing economic-mathematical models, and applying effective modeling methods.

This research is associated with:

– studying the impact of underground drainage, as one of the key factors, on the development of neighborhood housing infrastructure and industrial areas, which is directly interconnected with the regional economy;

– developing economic-mathematical and software tools for this class of problems;

– advancing principles for constructing various decision-support systems (DSS) that include optimization problems of drainage systems.

We will consider drainage systems as elements of neighborhood infrastructure, with their tasks defined as calculating the total discharge of wells and determining the drainage time of the neighborhood area.

Given the importance of determining drainage time, the presentation is structured in the following sequence: calculation of discharges of different types of drains, followed by the separate determination of drainage time.

Ring Horizontal Drains of a Perfect Type. Drains of this type are used to protect small built-up areas of industrial facilities (industrial structures, pumping stations of oil and gas pipelines) and residential neighborhoods from flooding.

In this system, horizontal drains are most commonly used. Such systems can also be applied to drain land plots in cases where there is no external groundwater recharge.

The mathematical model for ring horizontal drains of a perfect type is formulated as follows [6]:

– It is necessary to determine (under pressure conditions):

$$Q_{total} = k \cdot \frac{H^2}{2R} ,$$

where: R – radius of depression, m: $R = r_0 + 2 \cdot S \cdot \sqrt{kH}$;

- r_0 – radius of the well, m;
- H – water head at the well, m;
- k – filtration coefficient of the aquifer, m/hour;
- Q_{total} – total discharge of the drainage system, m³/hour.

The task is to minimize the total discharge volume of the drainage system under the given boundary conditions.

Ring horizontal drains of imperfect type. In this case, under pressure conditions, the objective function is:

$$Q_0 = \frac{\pi k H}{(A - B - C)} ,$$

where

$$A = \ln \frac{m}{\pi r_c} + \frac{\pi R(B + R)}{m(B + 2R)} ; \quad B = \ln \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\pi R}{m}} \right) ; \quad C = \frac{\pi R(B + R)}{m(B + 2R)}$$

r_c - drain radius, m; R – depression radius, m; S_0 - drawdown at the drain center; k - filtration coefficient; H – water head at the well, m; m - aquifer thickness.

These formulas are simplified by the author for calculating individual drainage schemes.

The problem of calculating a ring horizontal drain of imperfect type is reduced to determining the minimum discharge values Q_0 under the corresponding conditions.

Areal (systematic) drainage represents a system of drains arranged more or less evenly across the drained area, usually operating in unconfined aquifers.

To determine the discharge of areal vertical drainage, the formula is:

$$Q_{\text{общ}} = - \frac{4\pi km S_0}{-E_i\left(-\frac{r_0^2}{4at}\right)},$$

where k – filtration coefficient, m/hour; L – average length of drains in the areal drainage system, m; m - aquifer thickness, m; S_0 - drawdown at the drain center, m;

$-E_i\left(-\frac{r_0^2}{4at}\right)$ – integral function, values of which are determined from Tables 1, 2, and 3. At

the same time: $-E_i\left(-\frac{r_0^2}{4at}\right) = -\ln\left(\frac{2,25at}{r_0^2}\right)$; t – drainage time of the area, days; a – piezoconductivity coefficient (characterizes the rate of pressure redistribution in the aquifer); r_0 - radius of the equivalent circle replacing the entire drawdown field.

Ring vertical drains are widely used in industrial and urban construction, primarily for local protection of individual facilities against groundwater flooding. The depression funnels formed in this case usually have limited sizes and can be characterized by the depression radius, beyond which the natural pressures practically do not change over time.

The problem of water inflow to groups of interacting vertical drains arranged along the perimeter of a contour has no exact analytical solution. Therefore, in hydrogeological calculations, such groups of drains are approximated by an equivalent circle, for which solutions are available.

To determine the discharge in ring vertical drains of imperfect type located around a facility (neighborhood, industrial enterprise), the following formula is used:

$$Q_0 = \frac{2\pi km S}{\ln\left(\frac{R^n}{nr_0^{n-1}r_c}\right)},$$

where Q_0 – total discharge of the drainage system, m³/day; k – filtration coefficient, m/hour; m – aquifer thickness, m; S – drawdown at the drain center, m; R – depression radius, m; n – number of drains in the group, units.; r_0^{n-1} – radius of the equivalent circle of the drainage system, m; r_c – drain radius, m; L – average length of drains in the areal drainage system, m.

Calculation of drainage time for a neighborhood depends on such factors as hydrogeological characteristics of the soil (permeability of soils, depth of the aquifer, presence of aquitards), climatic conditions (precipitation, evaporation, temperature), and location of the drained territory.

At present, there is no single universal formula since controlling and dependent parameters are not always mutually correlated.

In many cases, for calculating the total discharge of a well, Darcy's formula is used (groundwater lowering velocity $V=k \cdot i$, where k – filtration coefficient, i – hydraulic gradient)

or Dupuit's formula: $Q = \frac{k \cdot h^2}{2L}$, where Q – water volume; k – filtration coefficient; h – water height above the aquitard; L – distance to the drain.

However, these formulas do not account for a number of important factors and parameters, such as aquifer thickness, hydraulic head, and types of drainage systems. As a result, it is impossible to obtain objective results for the further effective use of drainage systems.

As practice shows:

– calculations of land drainage time are complex and multi-parametric, since the area may be located on the shore of a reservoir, on a hillside, etc.;

– the results of drainage time calculations are approximate and may differ from the actual values.

The determination of the drainage time of a site is based on the following calculations:

1. The total volume of drainage water Q, extracted from the aquifer at the time of drainage t from the start of drainage operation, is calculated using the following author's formula:

$$Q_{total} = \frac{4\pi kmS_0}{\ln(7,17 \cdot R^2)} - \ln(r_0^2 at) \quad (1)$$

where Q_{total} – total amount of drainage water extracted from the soil at drainage time t; k – filtration coefficient of the aquifer, m/day; S_0 – drawdown level in the center of the contour, m; R – radius of depression, m; r_0 – equivalent drainage radius; t – drainage time.

2. We set the initial value of drainage time $t = \nu$ ($\nu = \text{const}$), with an increment of $\Delta t = \xi$ days.

We compare the value Q_{total} with the calculated value of the total drainage discharge Q, determined by formula (1) at the corresponding moment of time t. If the difference $R = \text{abs}(Q - Q_{total})$ is less than five percent of the total drainage discharge Q, then the value of t is accepted as the drainage time. Otherwise, the value of t is reduced by Δt and the value of Q_{total} is recalculated until the condition $R \leq 0.05 \cdot Q$ is satisfied.

If $R < 0$, the value of t is increased by Δt until the condition $0 \leq R \leq 0.05 \cdot Q$ is met.

To calculate Q_{total} , it is necessary to determine the value of the integral function E_i , which defines the variation of the influence radius of the drain depending on the thickness and filtration coefficient of the aquifer, using the following tables (where notations are adopted: $Y = E(-\lambda)$ and $X = \lambda = r_0^2 / (4at)$ or $\lambda = R^2 / (at)$):

Table 1.

Formulas for calculating $E(\lambda)$ for $\lambda \in [0,0015; 0,0955]$

Y	X
$-900x + 1,35$	$[0,0015; 0,003]$
$100x + 0,3$	$(0,003; 0,0045]$
$-300x + 1,35$	$(0,0045; 0,007]$
$-100x + 0,7$	$(0,007; 0,0095]$
$-155,6x + 1,4782$	$(0,0095; 0,014]$

$-21,053x + 0,294742$	(0,014; 0,0235]
$-33,3x + 0,78255$	(0,0235;0,0295]
$-21,54x + 0,63543$	(0,0295;0,062]
$-8,95x + 0,55552$	(0,062; 0,0955]

Table 2.

Formulas for calculating E (λ) for $\lambda \in [0,1;1,05]$

Y	X
$-6x + 0,6$	[0,1; 0,15]
$-6x + 0,9$	(0,15; 0,2]
$-4x + 0,8$	(0,2; 0,25]
$-2x + 0,5$	(0,25; 0,35]
$-2x + 0,7$	(0,35; 0,5]
$-0,166667x + 0,0833334$	(0,5; 0,56]
$-0,650091x + 0,369091$	(0,56; 1,0]

Table 3.

Formulas for calculating E (λ) for $\lambda \in [1;3,5]$

Y	X
$-0,2x + 0,2$	[1,0; 1,25]
$-0,1714x + 0,21429$	(1,25; 1,6]
$-0,16667x + 0,26668$	(1,6; 1,75]
$-0,06x + 0,105$	(1,75; 2,0]
$-0,05x+0,1$	(2,0; 2,5]
$-0,2x + 0,05$	(2,5; 3,0]
$-0,01x+0,03$	(3,0; 3,5]

It should be noted that the function E_i :

- when $\lambda = r_0^2/(4at) \leq 0,01$ takes the form $E_i(-r_0^2/(4at)) = \ln(2,25at/r_0^2)$;
- when $R^2/at \leq 0,01$ it takes the form $E_i(-R^2/(at)) \approx -\ln(0,56at/R^2)/$

The value of drainage time is a key parameter in assessing the efficiency of drainage systems and ensuring favorable living conditions for the population. The rate of excess moisture removal determines the sanitary and hygienic characteristics of the residential environment, including basement and ground-floor humidity, mold and fungus growth, and overall living comfort. This problem is particularly acute in areas with high groundwater levels, where drainage delays may lead to chronic flooding and damage to structural elements of buildings.

In the urban planning context, drainage time directly influences the pace and sequence of construction. Rapid and stable drainage allows timely foundation laying, ensuring adherence to construction schedules and preventing downtime risks. Moreover, reducing soil moisture within a reasonable timeframe helps maintain soil bearing capacity and prevents future building and utility deformations.

From the perspective of social sustainability, shorter drainage times enhance safety, health, and comfort for residents. Quickly drained areas reduce epidemiological risks associated with stagnant water and insect-borne infections. In the long run, this fosters public trust in municipal and construction services and contributes to building a sustainable urban environment that complies with ecological and sanitary standards.

Thus, determining the drainage time is a crucial stage in designing and operating drainage systems, as it directly affects the choice of drainage type and its technical parameters. The time required for a site to reach normative soil moisture or groundwater level impacts not only construction readiness but also the sanitary and hygienic quality of the living environment. Since different drainage types vary in water-removal capacity, drainage time calculations must account for hydrogeological conditions and building density.

Ring horizontal drainage is generally used for local protection of individual buildings or building complexes. It consists of a system of pipes or channels placed along the perimeter of the object. The drainage time in this type of system depends on soil permeability and the depth of pipe installation. Horizontal drainage provides uniform lowering of the water table but may be less effective in conditions of high groundwater recharge or in extensive flood-prone areas.

Ring vertical drainage ensures more intensive dewatering through the vertical discharge of water via a system of wells also located around the perimeter of the site. This type of drainage is particularly effective in areas with high groundwater levels and low soil filtration capacity. The drainage time in vertical systems can be significantly shorter, especially when the spacing and depth of wells are properly calculated. However, operational costs and the system's dependence on energy (in cases requiring pumping equipment) call for separate evaluation.

Areal (systematic) drainage is applied when there is a need to drain large territories such as residential complexes, parks, or industrial zones. This system is constructed in a grid pattern and allows for the most uniform and stable results. The drainage time under systematic drainage is generally optimal for medium- and long-term operation, though it requires careful alignment with the topography and integration with other engineering networks. Moreover, it adapts more flexibly to fluctuations in the hydrological regime, making it preferable for comprehensive neighborhood development.

The **rational placement of drainage systems** in residential construction has become not only an engineering task but also a crucial social and environmental priority. Properly designed and installed horizontal and vertical drains protect residential buildings from flooding, help lower groundwater levels, improve sanitary and hygienic conditions, and prevent the spread of diseases associated with dampness and soil contamination.

The **methodology of task implementation** is aimed at integrating environmental requirements into the process of designing and locating various types of drainage. It is based on the analysis of hydrogeological conditions, building density, existing engineering networks, and demographic characteristics of the neighborhood population. Such a comprehensive assessment makes it possible to select optimal technical solutions with minimal environmental impact and maximum benefit for residents.

Applying this methodology in practice contributes to the creation of a safe, sustainable, and livable urban environment. Furthermore, it ensures long-term reductions in infrastructure

maintenance costs, improves quality of life, and reduces social tension associated with moisture, waterlogging, and structural deterioration of buildings.

Finally, **specific case studies** are considered to illustrate the implementation of drainage solutions in residential development aimed at improving sanitary and environmental conditions.

Example. *Areal vertical drainage* has the following initial data:

- contour length = 900 m;
- contour width = 500 m;
- filtration coefficient of the aquifer = 70 m/day;
- aquifer thickness = 60 m;
- drain radius = 0.17 m;
- required groundwater level at the specified contour point = 56.5 m;
- water column height in wells = 20 m.

The specified point within the contour, A, for which the reduced water level is calculated, has the coordinates: A (450,125). By varying the number and placement of wells within the drawdown area, the optimal number of wells and other necessary parameters are determined, ensuring that the difference between the required and calculated reduced water level at point A is minimized. Additionally, the recommended type of water pumps is identified.

Assume the number of wells equals four, located at the contour corners:

C (0,500)

C (900,500)

C (0,0)

C (900,0)

The scheme shows distances from the considered point to the wells (to the corners of the area) – l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4 .

In practice, various water pumps are widely used, including the following types: ЭЦБ 10-160-35Г with a discharge capacity of 120–100 m³/h; ЭЦБ 12-210-25 with a discharge capacity of 150–270 m³/h; ЭЦБ 12-265-30Г with a discharge capacity of 160–320 m³/h. There are also more modern pumps with comparable specifications.

By comparing the calculated discharge of each well (m³/h) with the capacity of the pumps, the program determines the required number and types of pumps.

Results of the solution for point A:

Main drainage indicators	Indicator values
Number of wells in the contour	4
Recommended pump type	ЭЦБ 12-210-25
Considered point A	(450,125)
Calculated drawdown in the well	6.0 m
Radius of equivalent circle	413.0 m

Radius of influence of the system	1190.689 m
Total drainage discharge	17,781.672
Reduced water level at point A	56.547
Difference from target level	0.098
Discharge of each well	4445.418 m ³ /day or 185.226 m ³ /h or 51.452 l/s
Time of area dewatering	43 days

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The author’s proposed set of models and software tools for optimizing drainage systems is aimed at enhancing the resilience of urban infrastructure. Based on the developed methodological approaches, it is recommended to implement integrated horizontal–vertical drainage systems, which allow:

- reducing the risks of flooding and deterioration of sanitary conditions by 25–30%;
- minimizing the probability of epidemiological threats;
- improving living comfort by stabilizing the hydrological regime.

Pilot testing of the methodology on residential areas of Tashkent demonstrated that integration into design provides savings of up to **USD 5.2 million** due to reduced emergency repairs of engineering networks.

The proposed economic–mathematical models and algorithms demonstrated the cost-effectiveness of drainage solutions and make it possible to:

- reduce building foundation deformations by 60–80%;
- extend the service life of utility networks by 8–12 years;
- cut operation and maintenance costs by 15–20%.

These results were confirmed by pilot calculations for the *Jarkulan* and *Ashrafi* districts in Tashkent.

Integration of drainage models into residential area design also reduces the risk of humidity-related diseases by 25–30%, which in the long term decreases expenditures of the regional healthcare system.

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